

Condensation of Malonic Acid with Phenols and Substituted Phenols

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Malonic acid has been condensed with a number of phenols in presence of phosphorus oxychloride at 115°–120° to form diaryl esters which have been submitted to double Fries rearrangement yielding 1 : 3 diketones.

Thomas (II), Shamma and Fernelius¹ reported the condensation of *p*-cresol with malonic acid in which they obtained *p*-cresyl malonate (A, R = CH₃) as the product. This *p*-cresyl malonate on treatment with AlCl₃ in presence of chlorobenzene as solvent yielded 4-hydroxy coumarin instead of the diketone (B, R = CH₃).

In the present communication, the authors have described the condensation of malonic acid with phenols like *p*-cresol, *p*-chlorophenol, 4-chloro-*m*-cresol, chloroxylenol, and β -naphthol. The condensation of malonic acid with the aforementioned phenols in presence of phosphorus oxychloride at 150°–200° led to the formation of the corresponding

1. Thomas II, Shamma and Fernelius, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 5864.

diaryl esters (I). The esters obtained by the condensation of malonic acid with the phenols have been subjected to double Fries rearrangement in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride yielding crystalline 1 : 3 diketones of the type (II) in good yield.

EXPERIMENTAL

Di-p-cresyl malonate (I, R = R₁ = R₃ = H; R₂ = CH₃): Malonic acid (5.25 g.) and *p*-cresol (12.7 g.) were placed in a 200 ml. round-bottomed flask equipped with a thermometer and a reflux condenser protected by a drying tube. The flask was heated to 115°–120° in an oil bath, phosphorus oxychloride (10 g.) was added dropwise to the hot mixture. Towards the end of the addition the vigorous bubbling due to the evolution of HCl subsided. After heating for 2–3 hrs at 115°–120°, the dark reaction mixture was allowed to cool, when a reddish brown material containing crystals was obtained.

The crystalline material was scraped away from the black resin and mixed with 250 g. of ice. The dark orange crystals were then filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 69° (Found : C, 71.5; H, 6.4; C₁₇H₁₆O₄ requires C, 71.83; H, 5.63%).

All the esters of malonic acid were prepared by the method as described for *di-p-cresyl malonate*.

The products of condensation of other phenols and substituted phenols with malonic acid are described in Table I.

TABLE I

Phenols and Substituted phenols	Condensation products	Formula	m.p.	Analysis	
				Required	Found
<i>p</i> -chlorophenol	Di-(<i>p</i> -chloro phenyl)-malonate (I, R = R ₁ = R ₃ = H; R ₂ = Cl)	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₄ Cl ₂	122°	C, 55.38 H, 3.08	55.72 3.51
Chloro-xyleneol	Di-(chloro-xylenyl) malonate (I, R = H; R ₁ = R ₃ = CH ₃ ; R ₂ = Cl)	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₄ Cl ₂	127°	C, 59.84 H, 4.72	59.73 4.71
<i>β</i> -Naphthol	Di- <i>β</i> -naphthyl) malonate	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ O ₄	145°	C, 77.55 H, 4.49	77.20 4.43
4-Chloro- <i>m</i> -cresol	Di-(<i>p</i> -cl- <i>m</i> -cresyl) malonate (I, R = R ₁ = H; R ₂ = Cl; R ₃ = CH ₃).	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₄ Cl ₂	95°	C, 57.78 H, 3.96	57.58 3.85

Synthesis of 1 : 3 Diketones by Double Fries Rearrangement: 1 : 3 Bis-(2-hydroxy-5-methyl phenyl)-propane 1,3 dione—Di-*p*-cresyl malonate (3 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (3 g.) were placed in a 100 ml. round bottomed flask equipped with a calcium chloride guard tube. The flask with the contents was heated to 130°–140° for 3–4 hours. The cold reaction mixture was decomposed by ice and conc. hydrochloric acid and was kept overnight. The product was then extracted with ether. The yellowish product obtained was treated with 5% sodium hydroxide solution in which it was found to be soluble. It was filtered and the filtrate acidified when the diketone

separated out. This was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 260°. It gave a red colouration with FeCl_3 solution. (Found : C, 71.5; H, 6.4. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C 71.83; H, 5.63%).

The 2 : 4 D. N. P. H. crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 262° (Found : N, 16.8; $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_8$ requires N, 17.4%).

The other diketones obtained by Fries rearrangement are described in Table II.

TABLE II

Diaryl esters	Rearranged products— 1,3 diones	Formula	Analysis		Derivative
			Required	Found	
Di-(<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl) malonate.	1,3 bis-(2-hydroxy-5-chloro phenyl) propane-1 : 3 dione, m.p. 268° (II, R = R ₁ = R ₃ = H; R ₂ = Cl)	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2$	C, 55.38 H, 3.08	55.81 3.16	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 220° (Found : N, 16.0. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_8\text{Cl}_2$ requires N, 16.35%).
Di-(chloro xylenyl) malonate.	1,3 bis-(2-hydroxy-5-chloro-4 : 6-dimethyl phenyl)-propane-1 : 3 dione, m.p. 120° (II, R=H; R ₁ =R ₃ =CH ₃ ; R ₂ = Cl).	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2$	C, 59.84 H, 4.72	59.63 4.51	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 250° (Found : N, 15.00. $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_{10}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_8$ requires N, 15.11%).
Di-(β -naphthyl) malonate.	1,3 bis-(2-hydroxy naphthyl) propane-1 : 3 dione, m.p. 250°.	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$	C, 77.55 H, 4.49	77.30 4.33	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 289° (Found : N, 15.6. $\text{C}_{35}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_8$ requires N, 15.64%).
Di-(<i>p</i> -chloro- <i>m</i> -cresyl) malonate.	1,3 bis-(2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro phenyl) propane-1 : 3-dione (II, R = R ₃ = H; R ₁ = CH ₃ , R ₂ = Cl) or 1,3 bis-(2-hydroxy-6-methyl-5-chloro phenyl)-propane-1 : 3 dione (II, R=R ₁ =H; R ₂ =Cl; R ₃ =CH ₃), m.p. 250°.	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2$	C, 57.78 H, 3.96	57.71 3.84	2 : 4 D.N.P.H., m.p. 260° (Found : N, 15.8. $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_{10}\text{Cl}_2\text{N}_8$ requires N, 15.71%).

